

Supplementary Information

S.1. Overview simulated scenarios

Consumption level	Year	Convergence	Green electricity	Structural change	Organic agriculture	Plant-based diet	Scenario name
$\frac{11000\text{€}}{\text{person} * \text{year}}$	2040	complete	no	no	no	no	1111111
$\frac{11000\text{€}}{\text{person} * \text{year}}$	2040	interregional	no	no	no	no	1121111
$\frac{11000\text{€}}{\text{person} * \text{year}}$	2040	intraregional	no	no	no	no	1131111
$\frac{11000\text{€}}{\text{person} * \text{year}}$	2040	complete	yes	no	no	no	1112111
$\frac{11000\text{€}}{\text{person} * \text{year}}$	2040	interregional	yes	no	no	no	1122111
$\frac{11000\text{€}}{\text{person} * \text{year}}$	2040	intraregional	yes	no	no	no	1132111
$\frac{11000\text{€}}{\text{person} * \text{year}}$	2040	complete	no	yes	no	no	1111211
$\frac{11000\text{€}}{\text{person} * \text{year}}$	2040	interregional	no	yes	no	no	1121211
$\frac{11000\text{€}}{\text{person} * \text{year}}$	2040	intraregional	no	yes	no	no	1131211
$\frac{11000\text{€}}{\text{person} * \text{year}}$	2040	complete	no	no	yes	no	1111121
$\frac{11000\text{€}}{\text{person} * \text{year}}$	2040	interregional	no	no	yes	no	1121121
$\frac{11000\text{€}}{\text{person} * \text{year}}$	2040	intraregional	no	no	yes	no	1131121
$\frac{11000\text{€}}{\text{person} * \text{year}}$	2040	complete	no	no	no	yes	1111112
$\frac{11000\text{€}}{\text{person} * \text{year}}$	2040	interregional	no	no	no	yes	1121112
$\frac{11000\text{€}}{\text{person} * \text{year}}$	2040	intraregional	no	no	no	yes	1131112
$\frac{11000\text{€}}{\text{person} * \text{year}}$	2040	complete	yes	yes	yes	yes	1112222
$\frac{11000\text{€}}{\text{person} * \text{year}}$	2040	interregional	yes	yes	yes	yes	1122222
$\frac{11000\text{€}}{\text{person} * \text{year}}$	2040	intraregional	yes	yes	yes	yes	1132222
$\frac{11000\text{€}}{\text{person} * \text{year}}$	2060	complete	no	no	no	no	1211111
$\frac{11000\text{€}}{\text{person} * \text{year}}$	2060	interregional	no	no	no	no	1221111
$\frac{11000\text{€}}{\text{person} * \text{year}}$	2060	intraregional	no	no	no	no	1231111
$\frac{11000\text{€}}{\text{person} * \text{year}}$	2060	complete	yes	no	no	no	1212111
$\frac{11000\text{€}}{\text{person} * \text{year}}$	2060	interregional	yes	no	no	no	1222111
$\frac{11000\text{€}}{\text{person} * \text{year}}$	2060	intraregional	yes	no	no	no	1232111
$\frac{11000\text{€}}{\text{person} * \text{year}}$	2060	complete	no	yes	no	no	1211211

<u>11000€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2060	interregional	no	yes	no	no	1221211
<u>11000€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2060	intraregional	no	yes	no	no	1231211
<u>11000€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2060	complete	no	no	yes	no	1211121
<u>11000€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2060	interregional	no	no	yes	no	1221121
<u>11000€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2060	intraregional	no	no	yes	no	1231121
<u>11000€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2060	complete	no	no	no	yes	1211112
<u>11000€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2060	interregional	no	no	no	yes	1221112
<u>11000€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2060	intraregional	no	no	no	yes	1231112
<u>11000€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2060	complete	yes	yes	yes	yes	1212222
<u>11000€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2060	interregional	yes	yes	yes	yes	1222222
<u>11000€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2060	intraregional	yes	yes	yes	yes	1232222
<u>11000€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2100	complete	no	no	no	no	1311111
<u>11000€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2100	interregional	no	no	no	no	1321111
<u>11000€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2100	intraregional	no	no	no	no	1331111
<u>11000€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2100	complete	yes	no	no	no	1312111
<u>11000€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2100	interregional	yes	no	no	no	1322111
<u>11000€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2100	intraregional	yes	no	no	no	1332111
<u>11000€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2100	complete	no	yes	no	no	1311211
<u>11000€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2100	interregional	no	yes	no	no	1321211
<u>11000€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2100	intraregional	no	yes	no	no	1331211
<u>11000€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2100	complete	no	no	yes	no	1311121
<u>11000€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2100	interregional	no	no	yes	no	1321121
<u>11000€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2100	intraregional	no	no	yes	no	1331121
<u>11000€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2100	complete	no	no	no	yes	1311112
<u>11000€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2100	interregional	no	no	no	yes	1321112
<u>11000€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2100	intraregional	no	no	no	yes	1331112
<u>11000€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2100	complete	yes	yes	yes	yes	1312222
<u>11000€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2100	interregional	yes	yes	yes	yes	1322222
<u>11000€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2100	intraregional	yes	yes	yes	yes	1332222
<u>15400€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2040	complete	no	no	no	no	2111111
<u>15400€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2040	interregional	no	no	no	no	2121111

<u>15400€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2040	intraregional	no	no	no	no	2131111
<u>15400€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2040	complete	yes	no	no	no	2112111
<u>15400€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2040	interregional	yes	no	no	no	2122111
<u>15400€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2040	intraregional	yes	no	no	no	2132111
<u>15400€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2040	complete	no	yes	no	no	2111211
<u>15400€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2040	interregional	no	yes	no	no	2121211
<u>15400€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2040	intraregional	no	yes	no	no	2131211
<u>15400€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2040	complete	no	no	yes	no	2111121
<u>15400€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2040	interregional	no	no	yes	no	2121121
<u>15400€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2040	intraregional	no	no	yes	no	2131121
<u>15400€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2040	complete	no	no	no	yes	2111112
<u>15400€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2040	interregional	no	no	no	yes	2121112
<u>15400€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2040	intraregional	no	no	no	yes	2131112
<u>15400€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2040	complete	yes	yes	yes	yes	2112222
<u>15400€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2040	interregional	yes	yes	yes	yes	2122222
<u>15400€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2040	intraregional	yes	yes	yes	yes	2132222
<u>15400€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2060	complete	no	no	no	no	2211111
<u>15400€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2060	interregional	no	no	no	no	2221111
<u>15400€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2060	intraregional	no	no	no	no	2231111
<u>15400€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2060	complete	yes	no	no	no	2212111
<u>15400€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2060	interregional	yes	no	no	no	2222111
<u>15400€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2060	intraregional	yes	no	no	no	2232111
<u>15400€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2060	complete	no	yes	no	no	2211211
<u>15400€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2060	interregional	no	yes	no	no	2221211
<u>15400€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2060	intraregional	no	yes	no	no	2231211
<u>15400€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2060	complete	no	no	yes	no	2211121
<u>15400€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2060	interregional	no	no	yes	no	2221121
<u>15400€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2060	intraregional	no	no	yes	no	2231121
<u>15400€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2060	complete	no	no	no	yes	2211112
<u>15400€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2060	interregional	no	no	no	yes	2221112
<u>15400€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2060	intraregional	no	no	no	yes	2231112

<u>15400€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2060	complete	yes	yes	yes	yes	2212222
<u>15400€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2060	interregional	yes	yes	yes	yes	2222222
<u>15400€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2060	intraregional	yes	yes	yes	yes	2232222
<u>15400€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2100	complete	no	no	no	no	2311111
<u>15400€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2100	interregional	no	no	no	no	2321111
<u>15400€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2100	intraregional	no	no	no	no	2331111
<u>15400€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2100	complete	yes	no	no	no	2312111
<u>15400€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2100	interregional	yes	no	no	no	2322111
<u>15400€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2100	intraregional	yes	no	no	no	2332111
<u>15400€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2100	complete	no	yes	no	no	2311211
<u>15400€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2100	interregional	no	yes	no	no	2321211
<u>15400€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2100	intraregional	no	yes	no	no	2331211
<u>15400€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2100	complete	no	no	yes	no	2311121
<u>15400€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2100	interregional	no	no	yes	no	2321121
<u>15400€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2100	intraregional	no	no	yes	no	2331121
<u>15400€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2100	complete	no	no	no	yes	2311112
<u>15400€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2100	interregional	no	no	no	yes	2321112
<u>15400€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2100	intraregional	no	no	no	yes	2331112
<u>15400€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2100	complete	yes	yes	yes	yes	2312222
<u>15400€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2100	interregional	yes	yes	yes	yes	2322222
<u>15400€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2100	intraregional	yes	yes	yes	yes	2332222
<u>6600€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2040	complete	no	no	no	no	3111111
<u>6600€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2040	interregional	no	no	no	no	3121111
<u>6600€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2040	intraregional	no	no	no	no	3131111
<u>6600€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2040	complete	yes	no	no	no	3112111
<u>6600€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2040	interregional	yes	no	no	no	3122111
<u>6600€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2040	intraregional	yes	no	no	no	3132111
<u>6600€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2040	complete	no	yes	no	no	3111211
<u>6600€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2040	interregional	no	yes	no	no	3121211
<u>6600€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2040	intraregional	no	yes	no	no	3131211
<u>6600€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2040	complete	no	no	yes	no	3111121

<u>6600€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2040	interregional	no	no	yes	no	3121121
<u>6600€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2040	intraregional	no	no	yes	no	3131121
<u>6600€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2040	complete	no	no	no	yes	3111112
<u>6600€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2040	interregional	no	no	no	yes	3121112
<u>6600€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2040	intraregional	no	no	no	yes	3131112
<u>6600€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2040	complete	yes	yes	yes	yes	3112222
<u>6600€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2040	interregional	yes	yes	yes	yes	3122222
<u>6600€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2040	intraregional	yes	yes	yes	yes	3132222
<u>6600€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2060	complete	no	no	no	no	3211111
<u>6600€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2060	interregional	no	no	no	no	3221111
<u>6600€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2060	intraregional	no	no	no	no	3231111
<u>6600€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2060	complete	yes	no	no	no	3212111
<u>6600€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2060	interregional	yes	no	no	no	3222111
<u>6600€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2060	intraregional	yes	no	no	no	3232111
<u>6600€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2060	complete	no	yes	no	no	3211211
<u>6600€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2060	interregional	no	yes	no	no	3221211
<u>6600€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2060	intraregional	no	yes	no	no	3231211
<u>6600€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2060	complete	no	no	yes	no	3211121
<u>6600€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2060	interregional	no	no	yes	no	3221121
<u>6600€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2060	intraregional	no	no	yes	no	3231121
<u>6600€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2060	complete	no	no	no	yes	3211112
<u>6600€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2060	interregional	no	no	no	yes	3221112
<u>6600€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2060	intraregional	no	no	no	yes	3231112
<u>6600€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2060	complete	yes	yes	yes	yes	3212222
<u>6600€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2060	interregional	yes	yes	yes	yes	3222222
<u>6600€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2060	intraregional	yes	yes	yes	yes	3232222
<u>6600€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2100	complete	no	no	no	no	3311111
<u>6600€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2100	interregional	no	no	no	no	3321111
<u>6600€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2100	intraregional	no	no	no	no	3331111
<u>6600€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2100	Complete	yes	no	no	no	3312111
<u>6600€</u> <i>person * year</i>	2100	interregional	yes	no	no	no	3322111

$\frac{6600\text{€}}{\text{person} * \text{year}}$	2100	intraregional	yes	no	no	no	3332111
$\frac{6600\text{€}}{\text{person} * \text{year}}$	2100	Complete	no	yes	no	no	3311211
$\frac{6600\text{€}}{\text{person} * \text{year}}$	2100	interregional	no	yes	no	no	3321211
$\frac{6600\text{€}}{\text{person} * \text{year}}$	2100	intraregional	no	yes	no	no	3331211
$\frac{6600\text{€}}{\text{person} * \text{year}}$	2100	Complete	no	no	yes	no	3311121
$\frac{6600\text{€}}{\text{person} * \text{year}}$	2100	interregional	no	no	yes	no	3321121
$\frac{6600\text{€}}{\text{person} * \text{year}}$	2100	intraregional	no	no	yes	no	3331121
$\frac{6600\text{€}}{\text{person} * \text{year}}$	2100	Complete	no	no	no	yes	3311112
$\frac{6600\text{€}}{\text{person} * \text{year}}$	2100	interregional	no	no	no	yes	3321112
$\frac{6600\text{€}}{\text{person} * \text{year}}$	2100	intraregional	no	no	no	yes	3331112
$\frac{6600\text{€}}{\text{person} * \text{year}}$	2100	Complete	yes	yes	yes	yes	3312222
$\frac{6600\text{€}}{\text{person} * \text{year}}$	2100	interregional	yes	yes	yes	yes	3322222
$\frac{6600\text{€}}{\text{person} * \text{year}}$	2100	intraregional	yes	yes	yes	yes	3332222

SI Table 1: Scenario characteristics of all simulated scenarios along the scenario dimensions.

S.2. Boundary conditions

Default economic structural change

In the A-Matrix, all industrial processes improve energy efficiency by 5% regarding all energy inputs (fossil fuels, electricity, biomass energy). This is done by multiplying all energy inputs by a process efficiency coefficient (PEC).

Additionally, 10% of the non-electric energy demand of households and of certain industrial sectors (no. 3, 5, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 14, 15, 17, 21, 25) are substituted with electricity, linked to an energy efficiency gain of 50%.

Labor productivity

The key assumption behind the labor productivity developments in the scenario is a link between per capita consumption and regional economic development, with the latter being linked to higher labor productivities. Both assumptions are empirically grounded and are reflected in the country-based Exiobase3 data.

We make very optimistic assumptions regarding the future development of labor productivity in the context of degrowing consumption levels for the Global North as we assume that labor productivity in 2100 on the global scale is higher than in 2019 in the richest world region although average consumption on a global scale in 2100 is lower than in the center in 2019.

In scenarios with only intraregional convergence, we assume that labor productivity is somewhat lower as the majority of workers live in the semiperiphery and periphery. Likewise, lower labor productivity increases are assumed for ‘moderate’ and ‘strong’ DG compared to ‘weak’ DG.

SI Table 2 displays the different labor productivity assumptions for different scenario configurations.

Scale	Convergence	Sectoral labor productivity assumptions	
Soft DG	Full convergence, interregional convergence	Higher labor productivity scenarios $L_{prod.higher}$	Global labor productivity in 2100 is 1.3 times higher than labor productivity in the center in 2019
	Intraregional convergence	Upper medium labor productivity scenarios $L_{prod.upper\ medium} = 0.85 * L_{prod.higher}$	Global labor productivity in 2100 is 15% lower than in the higher labor productivity scenarios
Classic DG	Full convergence, interregional convergence	Lower medium labor productivity scenarios $L_{prod.lower\ medium} = 0.8 * L_{prod.higher}$	Global labor productivity in 2100 is 20% lower than in the higher labor productivity scenarios
	Intraregional convergence	Lower labor productivity scenarios $L_{prod.lower} = 0.75 * L_{prod.higher}$	Global labor productivity in 2100 is 25% lower than in the higher labor productivity scenarios

SI Table 2: Comparison of convergence and future labor productivity assumptions.

Land intensities

Land intensity developments are not differentiated according to consumption per capita levels to increase the comparability between the scenarios and avoid excessive complexity through varying boundary conditions.

A factor of 0.2 was applied for the default intensity improvements without additional policies. This means that land intensity for all land-demanding sectors and for all land types (forests, agricultural land, land used for energy generation) is reduced by 80% compared to the global average values in 2019. As a result, the global agricultural sector is 2.85 times more productive in terms of agricultural land use than the agricultural sector of the center in 2019, and the global forestry sector is 3.63 times more productive in terms of forest land use than the forestry sector of the center in 2019. Land intensity of infrastructure in the model is driven by household demand and remains constant which could lead to an overestimation of infrastructure land demand relative to other land demands. However, water-based renewable energy technologies, notably hydropower, are assumed to have a land-intensity of zero although infrastructure needs

to build the plants might result in additional land-use change not represented, which reduces the possible overestimation.

Resources

Default model assumptions that are not changed in the simulations include (1) the absence of limits regarding the quantity of extracted mineral resources; (2) linearly increasing input factors in the resource extraction sector as resource depletion increases; and (3) fossil resources that are the sum of reserve estimates for coal as well as resource estimates for natural gas and oil according to the BGR (2020). Optimistically, the model assumes complete substitutability between different types of fossil fuels.

S.3. Supplementary Figures

S.3.1. Temperature change

Scenarios 1211111 to 1232222

Scenarios 1311111 to 1332222

Scenarios 2111111 to 2132222

Convergence

- complete
- ▲ interregional
- intraregional

Scenario

- 2111111
- 2111112
- 2111121
- 2111211
- 2112111
- 2112222
- 2121111
- 2121112
- 2121121
- 2121211
- 2122111
- 2122222
- 2131111
- 2131112
- 2131121
- 2131211
- 2132111
- 2132222

Scenarios 2211111 to 2232222

Convergence

- complete
- ▲ interregional
- intraregional

Scenario

- 2211111
- 2211112
- 2211121
- 2211211
- 2212111
- 2212222
- 2221111
- 2221112
- 2221121
- 2221211
- 2222111
- 2222222
- 2231111
- 2231112
- 2231121
- 2231211
- 2232111
- 2232222

Scenarios 2311111 to 2332222

Scenarios 3111111 to 3132222

Scenarios 3211111 to 3232222

Scenarios 3311111 to 3332222

S.3.2. Output

Scenarios 1311111 to 1332222

Convergence

- complete
- ▲ interregional
- intra-regional

Scenario

- 1311111
- 1311112
- 1311121
- 1311211
- 1312111
- 1312222
- 1321111
- 1321112
- 1321121
- 1321211
- 1322111
- 1322222
- 1331111
- 1331112
- 1331121
- 1331211
- 1332111
- 1332222

Scenarios 2111111 to 2132222

Convergence

- complete
- ▲ interregional
- intra-regional

Scenario

- 2111111
- 2111112
- 2111121
- 2111211
- 2112111
- 2112222
- 2121111
- 2121112
- 2121121
- 2121211
- 2122111
- 2122222
- 2131111
- 2131112
- 2131121
- 2131211
- 2132111
- 2132222

Scenarios 2211111 to 2232222

Scenarios 2311111 to 2332222

Scenarios 3111111 to 3132222

Convergence

- complete
- ▲ interregional
- intraregional

Scenario

- 3211111
- 3211112
- 3211121
- 3211211
- 3212111
- 3212222
- 3221111
- 3221112
- 3221121
- 3221211
- 3222111
- 3222222
- 3231111
- 3231112
- 3231121
- 3231211
- 3232111
- 3232222

Scenarios 3211111 to 3232222

Convergence

- complete
- ▲ interregional
- intraregional

Scenario

- 3211111
- 3211112
- 3211121
- 3211211
- 3212111
- 3212222
- 3221111
- 3221112
- 3221121
- 3221211
- 3222111
- 3222222
- 3231111
- 3231112
- 3231121
- 3231211
- 3232111
- 3232222

Scenarios 3311111 to 3332222

Convergence

- complete
- ▲ interregional
- intraregional

Scenario

- 3311111
- 3311112
- 3311121
- 3311211
- 3312111
- 3312222
- 3321111
- 3321112
- 3321121
- 3321211
- 3322111
- 3322222
- 3331111
- 3331112
- 3331121
- 3331211
- 3332111
- 3332222

S.3.3. Consumption M50C

S.3.4. Consumption B30C

S.3.5. Consumption T20S

S.3.6. Consumption M50S

S.3.7. Consumption B30S

S.3.8. Consumption T20P

S.3.9. Consumption M50P

